

A Study on Human Resource Management Practices of Select Sugar Mills in Tamilnadu

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Introduction

The human resource management practices have been one of the major functions of the management of every organization. In production oriented organizations like sugar mills, large number human resources have been employed in the production as well as other processes. In this context, management of human resources is considered as crucial as other management functions. The productivity of sugar mills is dependent not only on the plant and machinery but also the efficient service of the human resources. The human resource management practices include recruitment and selection, training and development, performance evaluation, compensation and rewards, employee security, employee participation, career planning and development welfare measures and industrial relations. In this study, an attempt has been made to analyze each of these practices of human resource management. The analysis made in this chapter has been divided into three parts – socio demographic factors, human resource management practices and job satisfaction.

Objectives of the Study

1. To measure the dimensions of Human Resource Management Practices in selected Sugar Mills of Tamil Nadu especially towards family income and family size
2. To study the employees perception towards HRM practices in sugar mills.

Limitations of the Study

The present study is confined to the selected sugar mills of Tamil Nadu only.

Research Methodology

1. Geographical area covered : Tamilnadu
2. Research Design : Descriptive style
3. Data Source : Both Primary and Secondary data
4. Sampling Unit : Employees of sugar mills
5. Research Instrument : Interview schedule

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1.1
Family Size and HRM Practices

HRM Practices	Source of variation	SS	DF	MS	F Value	P Value	Result
Recruitment and Selection	Between Groups	592.586	3	197.529	23.252	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	4060.694	478	8.495			
	Total	4653.280	481				
Training and Development	Between Groups	1693.168	3	564.389	43.313	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	6228.533	478	13.030			
	Total	7921.701	481				
Performance Evaluation	Between Groups	2687.001	3	895.667	50.591	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	8462.559	478	17.704			
	Total	11149.560	481				
Compensation and Rewards	Between Groups	2061.363	3	687.121	47.544	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	6908.241	478	14.452			
	Total	8969.604	481				
Employee Security	Between Groups	818.729	3	272.910	68.082	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	1916.085	478	4.009			
	Total	2734.813	481				
Employee Participation	Between Groups	33.408	3	11.136	2.793	0.040	Significant @ 5%
	Within Groups	1905.491	478	3.986			
	Total	1938.898	481				

Career Planning and Development	Between Groups	29.676	3	9.892	5.202	0.002	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	908.988	478	1.902			
	Total	938.664	481				
Welfare measures	Between Groups	646.108	3	215.369	33.935	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	3033.684	478	6.347			
	Total	3679.793	481				
Industrial Relations	Between Groups	121.258	3	40.419	2.856	0.037	Significant @ 5%
	Within Groups	6764.280	478	14.151			
	Total	6885.537	481				

From the Table 3.21 it could be observed that there has been a significant association between family size and recruitment and selection practice followed by the selected sugar mills since the p value stating the relationship between family size and recruitment and selection practices has been found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The hypothesis that ‘there is no significant relationship between family size and the recruitment and selection practices followed by the selected sugar mills’ does not hold good. It is concluded that the perception of employees towards recruitment and selection process has been significantly different among the employees of the selected sugar mills in accordance with their family size.

It is observed that the p value stating the relationship between family size and the training and development practices followed by the selected sugar mills has been found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is a significant association between family size of the employees and their perception on training and development practices followed by the selected sugar mills.

It is found that the family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception towards performance evaluation has been significant as indicated by the p value of 0.000. The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted as the p value measuring the association between the family size of the employees and their perception on performance evaluation is less than 0.01.

The results of the analysis evinced that the p value indicating the relationship between family size of the respondents and their perception towards compensation and rewards is found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that the relationship between family size of the employees and their perception towards compensation and rewards is statistically significant.

The relationship between family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on employee security has been examined and the p value indicating the relationship between family size and perception of employees towards employee security has been found to be

0.000. The null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted since the p value is less than 0.01. The hypothesis that ‘family size of the employees and their perception on employee security are not significantly related’ does not hold good. It is concluded that there exists a significant relationship between family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on employee security.

It is revealed from the analysis that the p value denoting the relationship between family size of the employees and their perception towards employee participation is found to be 0.040. As the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It could be concluded that the association between family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception towards employee participation has been statistically significant.

The relationship between family size of the employees and their perception towards career planning and development has been indicated by the p value of 0.002. The p value less than 0.01 resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. The hypothesis that ‘there is a significant relationship between family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on career planning and development’ holds good. It is concluded that there exists a statistically significant relationship between family size of the employees and their perception on career planning and development.

It could be understood from the analysis that the p value highlighting the association between the family size of the employees and their perception on welfare measures is found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted. It is thus concluded that the relationship between family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on career planning and development is significant.

The relationship between family size of the employees and their perception on industrial relations has been tested and the p value denoting the relationship between family size of the employees and their perception towards industrial relations has been found to be 0.037. The p value is less than 0.05 which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Since the alternative hypothesis is accepted, it could be concluded that there exists a significant relationship between family size of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on industrial relations.

Table 1.2
Family Income and HRM Practices

HRM Practices	Source of variation	SS	DF	MS	F Value	P Value	Result
Recruitment and Selection	Between Groups	286.445	3	95.482	10.452	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	4366.835	478	9.136			
	Total	4653.280	481				
Training and Development	Between Groups	365.338	3	121.779	7.704	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	7556.363	478	15.808			
	Total	7921.701	481				

Performance Evaluation	Between Groups	1088.172	3	362.724	17.232	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	10061.388	478	21.049			
	Total	11149.560	481				
Compensation and Rewards	Between Groups	1351.578	3	450.526	28.269	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	7618.025	478	15.937			
	Total	8969.604	481				
Employee Security	Between Groups	700.368	3	233.456	54.851	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	2034.445	478	4.256			
	Total	2734.813	481				
Employee Participation	Between Groups	34.512	3	11.504	2.887	0.035	Significant @ 5%
	Within Groups	1904.386	478	3.984			
	Total	1938.898	481				
Career Planning and Development	Between Groups	34.314	3	11.438	6.046	0.000	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	904.350	478	1.892			
	Total	938.664	481				
Welfare measures	Between Groups	99.087	3	33.029	4.409	0.005	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	3580.706	478	7.491			
	Total	3679.793	481				
Industrial Relations	Between Groups	191.550	3	63.850	4.559	0.004	Significant @ 1%
	Within Groups	6693.987	478	14.004			
	Total	6885.537	481				

It is understood from the Table 3.24 that there has been a significant association between family income per month and recruitment and selection practice followed by the selected sugar mills since the p value stating the relationship between family income per month and recruitment and selection practices has been found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The hypothesis that 'there is no significant relationship between family income per month and the

recruitment and selection practices followed by the selected sugar mills' does not hold good. It is concluded that the perception of employees towards recruitment and selection process has been significantly different among the employees of the selected sugar mills in accordance with their family income per month.

It is observed that the p value stating the relationship between family income per month and the training and development practices followed by the selected sugar mills has been found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is a significant association between family income per month of the employees and their perception on training and development practices followed by the selected sugar mills.

It is found that the family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception towards performance evaluation has been significant as indicated by the p value of 0.000. The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted as the p value measuring the association between the family income per month of the employees and their perception on performance evaluation is less than 0.01.

The results of the analysis evinced that the p value indicating the relationship between family income per month of the respondents and their perception towards compensation and rewards is found to be 0.000. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that the relationship between family income per month of the employees and their perception towards compensation and rewards is statistically significant.

The relationship between family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on employee security has been examined and the p value indicating the relationship between family income per month and perception of employees towards employee security has been found to be 0.000. The null hypothesis has been rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted since the p value is less than 0.01. The hypothesis that 'family income per month of the employees and their perception on employee security are not significantly related' does not hold good. It is concluded that there exists a significant relationship between family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on employee security.

It is revealed from the analysis that the p value denoting the relationship between family income per month of the employees and their perception towards employee participation is found to be 0.035. As the p value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It could be concluded that the association between family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception towards employee participation has been statistically significant.

The relationship between family income per month of the employees and their perception towards career planning and development has been indicated by the p value of 0.000. The p value less than 0.01 resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. The hypothesis that 'there is a significant relationship between family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on career planning and development' holds good. It is concluded that there exists a statistically significant relationship between family income per month of the employees and their perception on career planning and development.

It could be understood from the analysis that the p value highlighting the association between the family income per month of the employees and their perception on welfare measures is found to be 0.005. Since the p value is less than 0.01, it falls in the rejection region. Hence, the null hypothesis

has been rejected and the alternative hypothesis has been accepted. It is thus concluded that the relationship between family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on career planning and development is significant.

The relationship between family income per month of the employees and their perception on industrial relations has been tested and the p value denoting the relationship between family income per month of the employees and their perception towards industrial relations has been found to be 0.004. The p value is less than 0.01 which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Since the alternative hypothesis is accepted, it could be concluded that there exists a significant relationship between family income per month of the employees of the selected sugar mills and their perception on industrial relations.

Conclusion

This article covers the relationship between family size and family income with Human Resources Practices. From this research family income and family size affects the working habits of the employees in sugar mill.